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Derivation and validation of a reference data-based real gas model for hydrogen

Sebastian Weiss^{a,b,*}, Jiri Polansky^c, Markus Bär^a, Kilian Oberleithner^b,
Sonja Schmelter^a

^a Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Abbestr. 2-12, 10578 Berlin, Germany

^b Institute of Fluid Dynamics and Technical Acoustics, Technische Universität Berlin, Müller-Breslau-Straße 8, 10623 Berlin, Germany

^c MECAS ESI, Part of ESI Group, Brojova 2113, 32600 Pilsen, Czech Republic

HIGHLIGHTS

- Development of new correlation equations for thermophysical properties of hydrogen.
- Accuracy has been improved comparing with other real gas models.
- Validation of real gas model in numerical simulation of critical flow Venturi nozzle.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogen plays an important role for the decarbonization of the energy sector. In its gaseous form, it is stored at pressures of up to 1000 bar at which real gas effects become relevant. To capture these effects in numerical simulations, accurate real gas models are required. In this work, new correlation equations for relevant hydrogen properties are developed based on the Reference Fluid Thermodynamic and Transport Properties Database (REFPROP). Within the regarded temperature (150–400 K) and pressure (0.1–1000 bar) range, this approach yields a substantially improved accuracy compared to other data-based correlations. Furthermore, the developed equations are validated in a numerical simulation of a critical flow Venturi nozzle. The results are in much better accordance with experimental data compared to a cubic equation of state model. In addition, the simulation is even slightly faster.

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* Corresponding author. Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Abbestr. 2-12, 10578 Berlin, Germany.

E-mail address: sebastian.weiss@ptb.de (S. Weiss).

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Introduction

The transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources constitutes a major challenge for society to which hydrogen can make a significant contribution [1,2]. Hydrogen is a promising energy carrier for use in climate-neutral applications in industry and transport. It is widely regarded as a potential solution for the future of energy security and sustainability [3]. Due to its low volumetric energy density, gaseous hydrogen needs to be stored at considerably high pressures (up to 1000 bar). To monitor hydrogen consumption, a verifiable flow measurement is required. Critical flow Venturi nozzles (CFVNs) are a state-of-the-art secondary standard gas flow meter. For precisely predicting the mass flow rate of high-pressure hydrogen through CFVNs in numerical simulations, an accurate real gas model is required. Such a model needs to include all relevant real gas effects within the required pressure and temperature range, which is for CFVNs – based on simulation results – typically between 150 K and 400 K.

The thermodynamic properties of a real gas are described using an equation of state (EoS) model, mainly correlating the density with pressure and temperature. Here, the cubic EoS models display a big class that extends the ideal gas law by parameters accounting for intermolecular forces as well as effects of particle volume. Two prominent representatives are the models by Redlich and Kwong [4] and Peng and Robinson [5]. Both models can simply be expressed in terms of the critical properties and the acentric factor of the considered fluid. Due to their simple form, they are suitable for efficient use in simulation software. The Peng-Robinson EoS is already implemented in the simulation software OpenFOAM v2012 [6], which is used in this work. Nguyen et al. [7] recently proposed a real gas model based on the modified Soave-Redlich-Kwong EoS [8,9] – an extension of the classical Redlich-Kwong EoS regarding the vapor-liquid equilibrium behavior of mixtures – for the simulation of reacting flows up to 300 bar in OpenFOAM v6 [10].

Normal hydrogen is commonly defined as a 3:1 mixture of the two isomeric forms ortho- and parahydrogen [11]. For temperatures above 150 K, this mixture ratio is in thermodynamic equilibrium, which is considered in this work. In Fig. 1, the density distribution of normal hydrogen is shown for pressures up to 1000 bar at a temperature of 300 K as predicted by the ideal gas law, the EoS by Redlich and Kwong, and the EoS by Peng and Robinson.

As a reference, the density of the most precise EoS model for normal hydrogen by Leachman et al. [11] is depicted, which is included in the Reference Fluid Thermodynamic and Transport Properties Database (REFPROP) [12,13]. REFPROP, developed by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), is a powerful tool for calculating thermophysical properties of industrially important fluids using the most accurate models available. At pressures beyond 200 bar, the ideal gas curve highly overestimates the density and, hence, deviates from the real gas curves. The Peng-Robinson and the Redlich-Kwong EoS models follow the trendline of REFPROP. Yet they show a maximum deviation of 5.2% above and 7.2% below the reference density in the depicted pressure range,

Fig. 1 – Density distribution of normal hydrogen for different pressures at a constant temperature of 300 K. Comparison of three different gas models with the REFPROP data.

respectively. In terms of accurately predicting the mass flow rate in the context of critical nozzles, those deviations are unacceptably high. On the other hand, the accurate models included in REFPROP are generally too complex to be used in a numerical simulation without substantially slowing down the computation process. That applies to the commercial simulation software Ansys Fluent [14], where much slower convergence rates should be expected when using the implemented models of REFPROP. Therefore, simpler correlations for hydrogen properties that are based on the REFPROP data can be found in the literature. For the investigation of the dispersion behavior of cryogenic hydrogen, Petipas [15] proposed a theoretical model providing a correlation between the gas concentration and temperature. Shao et al. [16] developed a thermodynamical transfer model for the analysis of the boil-off loss in liquified hydrogen. In the context of high-pressure hydrogen filling station applications, Chen et al. [17] proposed a real gas EoS model of hydrogen by fitting the REFPROP data with only one correlation coefficient. In comparison with the reference data, the resulting correlation equation for density showed a maximum error of 1.1% and 3.8% within the temperature ranges of 253 K–393 K and 173 K–393 K, respectively. Bai-gang et al. [18] developed an EoS model for hydrogen gas to investigate the fuel consumption characteristics of hydrogen-fueled vehicles. In a hydrogen consumption calculation for storage pressures up to 700 bar, the error was less than 0.5% comparing with reference data from the NIST. Ding et al. [19] presented an accurate empirical equation for the real gas critical flow factor of hydrogen determined by nonlinear regression for a temperature range between 150 K and 600 K and pressures up to 1000 bar. The regression was based on an analytic solution of the real gas critical flow factor calculated by the EoS by Leachman et al. [11]. The ideal discharge coefficients resulting from the presented analytic equation for real gas critical flow factor and the real discharge coefficients according to ISO 9300 [20] were in good accordance with experimental data by Morioka et al. [21] and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) results by Nagao et al. [22] and Kim et al. [23]. Recently, Park et al. [24] developed correlation equations in a polynomial form with integer exponents

on eleven hydrogen properties (including density, internal energy, and viscosity) for potential use in numerical simulations of hydrogen filling processes. The correlation coefficients were determined using a machine learning approach by regressing the REFPROP data in a validity range of 224.15 K–372.15 K and 1 bar–1001 bar for temperature and pressure, respectively. The average and maximum relative error values of their correlation equations are below 0.3% and 2.5%, respectively (except for entropy). For entropy, the average and maximum relative error values are 1.95% and 8.98%, respectively.

Despite all the work done regarding this topic, the accuracy of the hydrogen property correlations still needs to be further improved for precisely simulating the flow in CFVNs. Moreover, there is currently no real gas model based on REFPROP available for hydrogen, which has already been integrated time-efficiently into a CFD software package. Therefore, new correlation equations for the relevant thermodynamic and transport properties of hydrogen based on REFPROP are developed in the present work. The equations are fitted in the relevant temperature and pressure range between 150 K and 400 K and 0.1 bar and 1000 bar, respectively, so that an acceptable accuracy of the correlations is reached for all regarded thermophysical properties. In a second step, the correlation equations are integrated into the CFD software OpenFOAM v2012 [6] and are validated in a test simulation case of a toroidal CFVN. Running time and accuracy of this new model are compared with other gas models and experimental data.

Methods

In Fig. 2 an overview of the development of a new real gas model for hydrogen is shown. In the following sections, the correlations for the thermophysical properties of hydrogen, as implemented in REFPROP, will be presented. Due to the complex structure of these correlations, new polynomial representations with simple exponents will be developed that are necessary for efficient use in numerical simulations.

Reference real gas model for hydrogen

The REFPROP thermophysical database includes the most accurate models for normal hydrogen and is considered the reference real gas model in this work. In the latest version 10.0, the EoS by Leachman et al. [11], the model for dynamic viscosity by Muzny et al. [25,26], and the model for thermal conductivity by Assael et al. [27] are implemented for normal hydrogen.

Leachman et al. [11] developed an empirical fundamental EoS based on the reduced Helmholtz free energy for parahydrogen, normal hydrogen, and orthohydrogen for pressures up to 20,000 bar and temperatures up to 1000 K. The reduced Helmholtz free energy is separated into an ideal part α^0 and a residual part α^r

$$\alpha(\delta, \tau) = \alpha^0(\delta, \tau) + \alpha^r(\delta, \tau) \quad \text{with} \quad \delta = \frac{\rho}{\rho_c} \quad \text{and} \quad \tau = \frac{T_c}{T}, \quad (1)$$

where δ and τ are the reduced density and the inverse of the reduced temperature and ρ_c and T_c are the critical density and the critical temperature, respectively. For normal hydrogen, the reduced Helmholtz free energy parts are as follows

$$\alpha^0(\delta, \tau) = \ln(\delta) + 1.5\ln(\tau) + a_1 + a_2\tau + \sum_{k=3}^N a_k \ln(1 - e^{b_k\tau}),$$

$$\alpha^r(\delta, \tau) = \sum_{i=1}^l N_i \delta^{d_i} \tau^{t_i} + \sum_{i=1}^m N_i \delta^{d_i} \tau^{t_i} e^{-\beta_i} + \sum_{i=m+1}^n N_i \delta^{d_i} \tau^{t_i} e^{\varphi_i(\delta - D_i)^2 + \beta_i(\tau - \gamma_i)^2}. \quad (2)$$

The parameters a_k and b_k for the ideal part as well as N_i , d_i , t_i , β_i , φ_i , D_i , and γ_i for the residual part are optimized according to a nonlinear regression of calculated ideal gas heat capacity data from the literature as well as experimental thermodynamic and caloric data for real hydrogen, respectively. Other thermodynamic properties, i. e. pressure, enthalpy, and entropy, can be expressed by using partial derivatives of α , as demonstrated by Span et al. [28] for nitrogen. The required derivatives for hydrogen can be found in the work by Ding et al. [19].

Muzny et al. [25,26] developed an experimentally-based correlation for the dynamic viscosity of hydrogen for

Fig. 2 – Overview of the development of a REFPROP data-based real gas model for normal hydrogen.

temperatures up to 1000 K and pressures up to 2000 bar using the following approach

$$\mu(\rho, T) = \mu_0(T) + \Delta\mu_{\text{excess}}(\rho, T) + \Delta\mu_c(\rho, T), \quad (3)$$

where μ_0 is the viscosity contribution for the limit of zero density. The excess term $\Delta\mu_{\text{excess}}$ represents the contribution of all relevant effects at elevated densities. The last term $\Delta\mu_c$ considers the behavior near the critical point. Muzny et al. omitted this term with the argument that it only affects a very small temperature and density range close to the critical point. For the critical nozzle flow considered in this work, this approach is suitable since pressure and temperature ranges are far away from the critical point. According to Muzny et al. the considered viscosity terms are expressed as

$$\mu_0(T) = \frac{0.021357\sqrt{MT}}{\sigma^2 S^*} \quad \text{with} \quad \ln(S^*) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \hat{a}_i (\ln(T^*))^i,$$

$$\Delta\mu_{\text{excess}}(\rho, T) = \frac{N_A \sigma^3}{M} \sum_{i=0}^6 \hat{b}_i (T^*)^{-1} \mu_0 \rho + \hat{c}_1 \rho^2 e^{\left(\hat{c}_2 T_r + \hat{c}_3 T_r^{-1} + \frac{\hat{c}_4 \rho_r^2}{\hat{c}_5 + T_r + \hat{c}_6 \rho_r^6} \right)}, \quad (4)$$

where M , σ , T^* , N_A , ρ_r , and T_r are the molar mass, length scaling parameter, reduced temperature, Avogadro constant, scaled density, and scaled temperature, respectively.

Assael et al. [27] developed a correlation of the thermal conductivity of hydrogen fitted to experimental data in the temperature and pressure range of up to 1000 K and 1000 bar, respectively. The thermal conductivity k can be expressed as a sum of three independent terms

$$k(\rho, T) = k_0(T) + \Delta k_{\text{excess}}(\rho, T) + \Delta k_c(\rho, T), \quad (5)$$

where the contributions are similarly defined as those of the viscosity in Eq. (3). Since the critical temperature for normal hydrogen ($T_c = 33.145$ K) is well below the considered fitting range, the critical enhancement term Δk_c is omitted for the thermal conductivity correlation. The first two terms in Eq. (5) are given by

$$k_0(\tau) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^6 A_{1,i} \tau^{-i}}{\sum_{i=0}^3 A_{2,i} \tau^{-i}} \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta k_{\text{excess}}(\delta, \tau) = \sum_{i=1}^5 \delta^i (B_{1,i} + B_{2,i} \tau^{-1}) \quad (6)$$

with the correlation coefficients $A_{1,i}$, $A_{2,i}$, $B_{1,i}$, and $B_{2,i}$.

Development of correlation equations

The correlations for the reduced Helmholtz energy (and accordingly for the thermodynamic properties) in Eq. (2) and for the dynamic viscosity in Eq. (4) contain exponential terms as well as terms with real number exponents that are more time-consuming to calculate in a computer system compared to simple arithmetic operations. Since the thermophysical properties need to be calculated on every mesh node in every time step in a CFD simulation, the direct implementation of those equations would result in a drastic slowdown of the computation. Therefore, new accurate correlations using simple terms are developed in this work that are suitable for efficient usage in computational flow simulations. As the correlation for the thermal conductivity in Eq. (6) only

contains exponents with integer values, the expression for the thermal conductivity does not require any modification.

Correlation for density

In the thermophysical model of OpenFOAM (v2012) [6], the two independent intensive thermodynamic properties are pressure and temperature, from which other properties are computed. However, the EoS model as well as the transport models for hydrogen are formulated explicitly in density and temperature (or their reduced forms). Hence, the density needs to be calculated iteratively from pressure and temperature by solving the following equation

$$p = \rho R_M T Z = \rho R_M T \left[1 + \delta \left(\frac{\partial \alpha^r}{\partial \delta} \right)_\tau \right] \quad \text{with} \quad R_M = \frac{R}{M}, \quad (7)$$

where $(\partial \alpha^r / \partial \delta)_\tau$ and R are the first partial derivative of α^r with respect to δ and the universal gas constant, respectively. Thus, the density is determined in a pre-processing step using the iterative regula falsi method with starting values for density based on the Peng-Robinson EoS model. The direct implementation of this iterative calculation procedure, including the aforementioned complicated form of α^r , is highly time-consuming. Hence, the density is approximated by a polynomial representation in pressure and temperature only using simple exponents, e. g. integers or half-integers. For the determination of appropriate exponents in pressure and temperature, the structure of the virial EoS is used. The virial EoS can be formulated as a series expansion of the compressibility factor Z in terms of the density (Leiden form) or pressure (Berlin form)

$$Z = \frac{p}{\rho R_M T} = 1 + B(T)\rho + C(T)\rho^2 + D(T)\rho^3 + \dots, \quad (8)$$

$$Z = \frac{p}{\rho R_M T} = 1 + B'(T)p + C'(T)p^2 + D'(T)p^3 + \dots \quad (9)$$

Starting with the Berlin form (Eq. (9)) and using the relations between the virial coefficients, as follows

$$B' = \frac{B}{R_M T}, \quad C' = \frac{C - B^2}{(R_M T)^2}, \quad D' = \frac{D + 2B^3 - 3BC}{(R_M T)^3}, \quad (10)$$

the inverse of the reduced density can be represented in polynomial form with respect to the reduced pressure $\psi = p/p_c$ and the inverse of the reduced temperature $\tau = T_c/T$, as given in the following

$$\frac{1}{\delta} = \rho_c R_M \left[\frac{T_c}{p_c} (\psi \tau)^{-1} + \frac{B}{R_M} (\psi \tau)^0 + \frac{C - B^2}{R_M^2} \frac{p_c}{T_c} (\psi \tau)^1 + \frac{D + 2B^3 - 3BC}{R_M^3} \frac{p_c^2}{T_c^2} (\psi \tau)^2 + \dots \right]. \quad (11)$$

Thus, the potential candidates for appropriate exponents in both ψ and τ are $-1, 0, 1$, and 2 . Combining the resulting four different exponents in ψ and in τ leads to a set of $J = 16$ correlation coefficients n_j that need to be determined for the calculation of the reduced density $\delta = \rho/\rho_c$

$$\delta(\psi, \tau) = \left[\sum_{j=1}^J n_j \psi^j \tau^{t_j} \right]^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

where p_j and t_j are the exponents of the reduced pressure and temperature, respectively. The unknown correlation coefficients n_i are calculated using the ordinary least squares method, as follows

$$x = (A^T A)^{-1} A^T b, \quad (13)$$

with $x = n_j \in \mathbb{R}^J$, $A = \left[\psi_k^{p_j} \tau_k^{t_j} \right] \in \mathbb{R}^{J \times K}$, and $b = 1/\delta_k \in \mathbb{R}^K$. Here, $J = 16$ is the number of correlation coefficients and $K = 1500$ is the size of the input data set consisting of 50 equidistant pressure values and 30 equidistant temperature values in the range between 0.1 and 1000 bar and 150 and 400 K, respectively. This is the relevant range for hydrogen flowing through CFVNs.

For the evaluation of the accuracy of the polynomial representation of the density, the mean and maximum percentage error between the approximated density and the density based on the EoS model by Leachman et al. [11] are calculated. The underlying evaluation data set is composed of 200 pressure and 100 temperature values (both equidistant) in the same range as the input data set. The calculated mean and maximum percentage errors are 0.117% and 2.01%, respectively.

The accuracy can be further increased by considering additional half-integer exponents within the range of the chosen integer exponents. The exponents -0.5 and 0.5 in ψ are added to the density correlation as a compromise between accuracy improvement of the correlation and limiting the number of correlation coefficients. Applying the ordinary least squares method (see Eq. (13)) for the new set of $\bar{J} = 6 \cdot 4 = 24$ correlation coefficients leads to improved mean and maximum percentage errors of 0.0133% and 0.107%, respectively. The resulting correlation coefficients for density $\rho = \rho_c \delta$ are displayed in Appendix A in Table A1.1. This newly developed polynomial representation of density serves as the input for other thermophysical property correlations.

Correlations for thermodynamic and transport properties

A general representation of a thermophysical property f using a polynomial equation can be expressed in δ and τ as follows

$$f(\delta, \tau) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_f} n_{f,j} \delta^{d_{f,j}} \tau^{t_{f,j}}. \quad (14)$$

The reduced density δ is calculated according to the correlation as derived in the previous section. The determination of adequate and simple exponents $d_{f,j}$ and $t_{f,j}$ is based on the

comparison with the initial formulation for the underlying thermophysical property. In case of the thermodynamic properties, the reduced Helmholtz energy formulas in Eqs. (1) and (2) by Leachman et al. [11] are used. In case of the dynamic viscosity, Eqs. (3) and (4) by Muzny et al. [25,26] are considered. Candidates of exponents for the target polynomial equation are found by either rounding real number exponents of the original equation or applying Taylor series to more complicated terms, e. g. exponential or logarithmic terms. This allows an individual treatment of each property in order to improve the accuracy of the correlation. Once the right set of N_f exponents is chosen, the correlation coefficients $n_{f,j}$ are calculated using the ordinary least squares method (as described in the previous section for density). Here, the variables in Eq. (13) are defined as follows: $x = n_{f,j} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_f}$, $A = \left[\delta_k^{d_{f,j}} \tau_k^{t_{f,j}} \right] \in \mathbb{R}^{N_f \times K}$, and $b = f_k \in \mathbb{R}^K$. The final correlations for the relevant thermophysical properties can be found in Appendix A in Tables A1.2, A1.3, and 1A.4.

For the specific entropies s , the input and evaluation data sets for pressure are not equidistant (as for the other properties) but have been chosen evenly spaced on a logarithmic scale generating a higher concentration of data points for lower pressures. This spacing is selected because the curve of specific entropy exhibits a high gradient with respect to pressure in the low pressure range and thus, considerably improves the accuracy of the correlation over an equidistant spacing.

The implementation of the real gas model into the CFD software OpenFOAM v2012 [6] is available at <https://gitlab1.ptb.de/methyinfra/hydrogen-real-gas-model>, an open source online GitLab repository hosted by Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), and is described in Appendix A.

Results and discussion

Hereinafter, the accuracy of the real gas model correlation will be quantified by means of the percentage error with respect to the REFPROP database. Furthermore, the developed equations are compared with other correlations for hydrogen from the literature. For the validation of the implemented real gas model, a numerical simulation of the hydrogen flow through a CFVN is conducted. The results of the real gas model are compared with experimental data and the EoS model by Peng and Robinson [5].

Accuracy of the real gas model

Fig. 3 visualizes the distribution of the percentual error of (a) density, (b) speed of sound, and (c) specific entropy correlation, respectively, from the reference data for the whole regarded pressure and temperature range.

Density is the most relevant thermophysical property in this work in two respects: it is the dominant quantity for the calculation of the mass flow rate in CFVNs and it serves as an input value for the other hydrogen properties of the real gas model. Thus, an accurate correlation for density is required for the entire pressure and temperature range. As shown in Fig. 3 (a), the deviation for density is within $\pm 0.1\%$, where the highest deviations only occur in the lower temperature band

Table 1 – Percentage errors of the correlation equations for the relevant thermophysical properties regarding the REFPROP data for the entire pressure and temperature fitting range.

	ρ	u	h	w	c_v
Mean error in %	0.0133	0.0012	0.0011	0.0045	0.0006
Max. error in %	0.107	0.018	0.011	0.112	0.006
	c_p	$\partial c_p / \partial T^a$	s	μ	
Mean error in %	0.0020	0.00001	0.0410	0.0008	
Max. error in %	0.046	0.0002	0.230	0.014	

^a For $\partial c_p / \partial T$ the absolute mean and max. errors are displayed.

Fig. 3 – Distribution of the percentage error in (a) density, (b) speed of sound, and (c) specific entropy of the correlation equation (subscript corr.) regarding the REFPROP data (subscript RP) for the entire pressure and temperature fitting range.

between 150 K and 200 K. The mean deviation is approximately 0.01% providing a high precision for the density calculation.

The speed of sound correlation, as depicted in Fig. 3 (b), is essential for the calculation of the real gas Mach number. The error distribution for w shows even better results than for ρ , represented by the light blue areas. This results in a mean deviation of below 0.005%. The highest deviation, which is approximately 0.1%, is located in the bottom left corner for low pressures and low temperatures.

The correlation for the specific entropy is presented in Fig. 3 (c). For the flow in CFVNs, entropy depicts an important quantity for the calculation of the real gas critical flow factor, as shown in the work by Ding et al. [19]. Due to its high

gradient in the low-pressure range, as previously discussed, acceptable accuracy could not be achieved with a conventional spacing of data points. However, accurate results have been attained by using logarithmic spacing instead, yielding a mean error of 0.041%. The color map reveals the highest deviation of below 0.24% for the highest pressure and the lowest temperature. Altogether, it clearly shows that in the proximity of the bounds of the depicted range, the deviations further increase. Thus, it is not recommended to extend the temperature and pressure ranges as this might lead to undesirably high deviations from the reference data.

Table 1 provides an overview of the percentage errors of the correlations for the relevant thermophysical properties in the considered pressure and temperature ranges. The mean and maximum errors are listed for density ρ , specific internal energy u , specific enthalpy h , speed of sound w , specific heat capacity at constant volume c_v and at constant pressure c_p , temperature derivative of specific heat capacity at constant pressure $\partial c_p / \partial T$, specific entropy s , and dynamic viscosity μ . As the values for $\partial c_p / \partial T$ are very close to zero, the absolute error is displayed instead of the relative error. The highest values in mean and maximum error are 0.041% and 0.23% for the specific entropy s , respectively.

A priori analysis of the real gas model

For a more detailed assessment of the results, the presented equations for density, speed of sound, and specific entropy are compared with other data-based correlations by Chen et al. [17] and Park et al. [24]. Fig. 4 displays the comparison of the percentage error for the density correlation developed in this work with those by Chen et al. [17] and by Park et al. [24] for pressures up to 1000 bar and at three different temperatures of (a) 200 K, (b) 300 K, and (c) 400 K.

The density correlation by Chen et al. depicts a maximum deviation of approximately $\pm 0.5\%$ from the reference data at temperatures of 300 K and 400 K in the entire pressure range. For the lowest temperature of 200 K, however, the maximum deviation increases close to 2.5%. The equation only contains one correlation coefficient and therefore, the order of magnitude of the deviation is acceptable. The correlation equation by Park et al. consisting of 21 coefficients, demonstrates a higher accuracy with the exception for very low pressures where the error is increasing. This might be due to the fact that the correlation only contains terms with integer exponents, which limits the adaptability to the reference data. Furthermore, the fitting range of the correlation by Park et al. is between 224.15 K and 372.15 K. This might explain the local peaks arising for 200 K and 400 K, as shown in Fig. 4 (a) and (c).

The correlation of this work has the smallest deviations from the reference data within the entire pressure and temperature range depicted. For reasons of clarity, the zoomed section in (b) exemplarily highlights the correlation distribution at 300 K. The maximum deviation is one to two orders of magnitude lower compared to the correlations by the other authors. The reason for the better accuracy might be that the presented correlations also contain terms with half-integer exponents.

Similar to density, the distribution of the deviations for the speed of sound correlations is shown in Fig. 5. Here, the

Fig. 4 – Distribution of the percentage error in density of correlations (subscript corr.) by Chen et al. [17], by Park et al. [24], and by the authors of this work regarding the REFPROP data (subscript RP) at a temperature of (a) 200 K, (b) 300 K, and (c) 400 K, respectively. Enlarged section in (b) shows the correlation of this work in more detail.

Fig. 5 – Distribution of the percentage error in speed of sound of correlations (subscript corr.) by Chen et al. [17], by Park et al. [24], and by the authors of this work regarding the REFPROP data (subscript RP) at a temperature of (a) 200 K, (b) 300 K, and (c) 400 K, respectively. Enlarged section in (b) shows the correlation of Park et al. and of this work in more detail.

correlation by Chen et al. reveals the highest offset from the REFPROP data yielding a maximum deviation of ca. 3.5% at a temperature of 200 K. The error further decreases for higher temperatures. The correlations by Park et al. and of this work equally demonstrate excellent accordance to the reference data. The zoom in (b) provides a deeper insight into the deviation distributions of the two correlations, exemplary for 300 K. The errors for the lowest temperature slightly increase but still remain in an acceptable range.

The error distribution for the specific entropy is depicted in Fig. 6 for the correlation by Park et al. and the correlation from this work. A correlation for the specific entropy has not been developed by Chen et al. and is therefore not visible in the diagram. The correlation by Park et al. shows errors of up to 8% in comparison with the REFPROP values, which is remarkably high when compared with their correlations for other properties. On the other hand, the correlation presented in this contribution provides deviations of up to two orders of magnitude lower, which is represented, for instance, in the enlarged section in (b). Presumably, this high difference in accuracy between the two correlations is mainly due to the different spacing methods (equidistant and logarithmic) of the data points for the determination of the correlation coefficients.

Altogether, the developed correlations of hydrogen properties demonstrate better accuracy regarding the REFPROP data compared to the correlations by Chen et al. [17] and Park et al. [24]. This improved accuracy is promising for the simulation of the flow in CFVNs, where a precise prediction of the mass flow rate is crucial.

A posteriori analysis of the real gas model

For the validation of the newly implemented real gas model, the computational domain of a toroidal nozzle in Fig. 7 is used. The flow scenario is chosen in conformity with the experimental setup of Morioka et al. [21], who investigated the flow characteristics of a toroidal CFVN with hydrogen gas at pressures up to 700 bar. The nozzle geometry is according to the ISO 9300 standard [20] and has a throat diameter d of 0.6 mm. The computational domain consists of a 5° wedge sector of the nozzle to represent a two-dimensional axisymmetric continuous flow. The inlet region encompasses a quarter circle with a radius of $2d$ and the outlet is located $7.14d$ downstream of the nozzle throat at the end of the divergent part of the nozzle.

The numerical simulation is conducted in OpenFOAM v2012 using the transient, compressible Navier-Stokes solver

Fig. 6 – Distribution of the percentage error in specific entropy of correlations (subscript corr.) by Park et al. [24] and by the authors of this work regarding the REFPROP data (subscript RP) at a temperature of (a) 200 K, (b) 300 K, and (c) 400 K, respectively. Enlarged section in (b) shows the correlation of this work in more detail.

Fig. 7 – Computational domain of the considered toroidal nozzle.

sonicFoam. For the temporal discretization, the implicit Euler method is used. For the spatial discretization, linear gradient schemes as well as linear and upwind divergence schemes are used. Turbulence is modeled with the γ - Re_{θ} transitional turbulence model by Langtry and Menter [29] based on the study by Weiss et al. [30]. The boundary layer is resolved using wall functions. Different throat Reynolds numbers are investigated in the range of $8.5 \cdot 10^3$ to $4.4 \cdot 10^6$ and $8 \cdot 10^3$ to $2.7 \cdot 10^6$ for ideal gas and real gas, respectively. The variation of the throat Reynolds number from case to case is realized by altering the value of the total inlet pressure. The total inlet pressure is constant for each individual flow case. The ratio of the static outlet to total inlet pressure, also referred to as the back pressure ratio (BPR), is fixed to a value of 0.5 to allow for a critical flow through the nozzle and to keep the position of shock waves in the divergent part of the nozzle. The total inlet temperature is kept constant at 300 K and the inlet turbulence intensity is set to 0.5%. At the walls, adiabatic no-slip boundary conditions are implemented.

Three different gas models are used for the hydrogen nozzle flow simulation: the ideal gas model, the real gas model by Peng and Robinson [5] as well as the real gas model as presented in this work. For selected flow cases with the ideal gas model, a grid independence study is conducted comparing three different refinement levels regarding the prediction of the discharge coefficient as the ratio of actual to theoretical mass flow rate. Based on this study, a mesh with approximately 175,000 hexahedral cells is selected for all considered flow simulations as the best compromise between accuracy and computational runtime.

The CFD results are presented in Fig. 8 in terms of the ideal discharge coefficient for different Reynolds numbers. It is defined as follows

$$C_D^i = \frac{\dot{m}}{C_i^* A^*} \frac{\sqrt{R_M T_0}}{p_0} \quad \text{with} \quad C_i^* = \sqrt{\kappa \left(\frac{2}{\kappa + 1} \right)^{\frac{\kappa+1}{\kappa-1}}}, \quad (15)$$

where \dot{m} , C_i^* , A^* , p_0 , T_0 , and κ are the mass flow rate, ideal critical flow factor, critical area, stagnation pressure,

Fig. 8 – Distribution of the ideal discharge coefficient for different Reynolds numbers. Comparison of the CFD results conducted with three different gas models for normal hydrogen (ideal gas (Δ), real gas by Peng and Robinson [5] (\square), and real gas of this work (\circ)) with the experimental work by Morioka et al. [21] (∇) and the ISO 9300 curves [20] ($- \cdot -$).

stagnation temperature, and ideal isentropic exponent, respectively. The numerical values are compared with the experimental data by Morioka et al. [21] and the C_D curves of the ISO 9300 [20].

In their experimental work, Morioka et al. [21] determined the ideal discharge coefficient using a critical nozzle type flowmeter. The experimental setup was equipped with automatic pressure controllers upstream and downstream of the nozzle to set the desired flow condition. Sensors upstream of the nozzle were used to measure the stagnation temperature T_0 and stagnation pressure p_0 . The mass flow rate \dot{m} was determined with a national standard gas flow calibration facility, where the total mass of the gas flown through the nozzle in a specific time was measured on a scale. The experimental value of C_D^i was equally calculated according to Eq. (15).

The curve of the ideal gas follows the trendline of the ISO 9300 in the entire Reynolds number range. The discharge coefficients of the real gas models start to deviate from the ideal gas curve at a specific Reynolds number and decrease with increasing values for Re . The model by Peng and Robinson predicts higher values of C_D^i compared to the experimental data by Morioka et al. and indicates a deviation from the ideal curve at a higher Reynolds number of ca. $6 \cdot 10^5$. The overprediction of the C_D^i values compared to the experimental curve is in accordance with the overprediction of density by the Peng-Robinson EoS compared to the REFPROP curve, as shown in Fig. 1. The results of the real gas model developed in this work are in good agreement with those of the experimental data, where the deviation point is at approximately $Re = 2 \cdot 10^5$. In terms of accuracy, the novel real gas model for hydrogen achieves better results than the Peng-Robinson model in comparison with experimental data for the flow through a CFVN.

Furthermore, in this numerical study, the computation for the new real gas model is slower compared to the ideal gas model but slightly faster compared to the real gas model by Peng and Robinson. This might be explained by the fact that for the calculation of density in the Peng-Robinson model, a cubic equation needs to be solved in every time step and on every mesh cell. For the new real gas model, the implemented correlation equation for density needs to be evaluated instead, which requires less time than solving the cubic equation. Consequently, it demonstrates convincing performance for the application in numerical simulations.

Conclusion

In this work, new correlation equations for relevant thermo-physical properties of hydrogen were developed based on the REFPROP database for the application in numerical simulations. The main findings of the new correlations are:

- Mean and maximum errors are below 0.041% and 0.23% within a broad temperature (150–400 K) and pressure (0.1–1000 bar) range.
- Errors slightly increase on the borders of validation range. Hence, extending this range should be handled carefully.
- Developed correlations demonstrate better accuracy compared to other data-based correlations.

- Improved accuracy is promising for simulations in high-pressure hydrogen applications.

Furthermore, the simple polynomial form of the correlations enables a fast calculation time relevant for use in CFD simulations. The developed equations were successfully implemented into the open source CFD software OpenFOAM. As a validation test case, a toroidal CFVN was investigated regarding the ideal discharge coefficient distribution for different Reynolds numbers. The results of the new real gas model were in best accordance with experimental data, compared with those of the ideal gas model, the Peng-Robinson EoS model, as well as with the standard curves of the ISO 9300. In addition, the simulation time was slightly faster compared to the simple Peng-Robinson EoS model.

Altogether, an accurate and time-efficient real gas model of hydrogen was made available in this work for the application in numerical simulations within a broad temperature and pressure range. This new real gas model could also be efficiently used in simulations of other hydrogen applications, e. g. hydrogen tank filling processes, hydrogen leakage and diffusion estimation or hydrogen free stream calculations. Furthermore, for applications operating in higher pressure or temperature ranges, e. g. hydrogen combustion, the real gas model could be extended by simply adjusting the correlation coefficients to the required range. For investigations close to the critical point of hydrogen, however, it is advised to enhance the presented correlation approach by considering additional correlation terms. Thus, a contribution was made to tackle the challenges in a variety of hydrogen-related engineering applications.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.03.073>.

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